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EFFECTIVE ASPECTS OF SOCIAL WORK ACTIVITY WITH DISABLE STUDENTS AT SCHOOLS UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

This article highlights the purpose of social protection of students with disabilities at schools, the use of social work techniques and technologies with those students, as well as increasing their dignity, protecting their rights and interests, creating a human environment without obstacles, sociological studies based on various relationships between micro, meso, eco, macro system elements that directly or indirectly have a social impact, serving to ensure effective integration and inclusiveness of the society. Also, theoretical experience of foreign countries, the active participation of social workers in school education by working together with students, their families, teachers, the public and other stakeholders in creating a healthy and friendly environment and thereby ensuring inclusive education are described.

Keywords: risk, disability, special education, exclusion, segregation, integration, inclusion, multidisciplinary support approach, assessment, "school-family- neighborhood-community" partnership, ecological system, mediation, peer group, consensus.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada maktablarda xavf guruhiga mansub o'quvchilarni ijtimoiy himoyalash maqsadida nogironligi bo'lgan o'quvchilar bilan ijtimoiy ish texnika va texnologiyalarni qo'llash, shuningdek, ularning qadr-qimmatini yuksaltirish, huquq va manfaatlarini himoya qilish, to'siqsiz insonparvar muhit yaratish, jamiyatga samarali integratsiya qilish va inklyuzivligini ta'minlashga xizmat qiluvchi bevosita yoki bilvosita ijtimoiy ta'sir etuvchi mikro, mezo, ekzo, makro tizim elementlari orasidagi turli munosabatlar negizidagi sotsiologik tadqiqotlar asoslantirilgan. Shuningdek maktab ta'limida ijtimoiy ishchilar o'quvchilar, ularning oilalari, o'qituvchilar, jamoatchilik va boshqa manfaatdor tomonlar bilan birgalikda ishlash orqali sog'lom, do'stona muhitni rivojlantirishda, bu bilan inklyuziv ta'limni ta'minlashda faol ishtiroki nazariy va xorijiy davlatlar tajribasi misolida batafsil tafsiflangan.

Kalit so'zlar: xavf, nogironlik, maxsus ta'lim, eksklyuziya, segregatsiya, integratsiya, inklyuziv, ko'p tarmoqli qo'llab-quvvatlash yondashuvi, baholash, "maktab-oila-mahalla-jamoatchilik" hamkorligi, ekologik tizim, mediatsiya, tengdoshlar guruhi, konsensus.

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ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ С УЧАЩИМИСЯ-ИНВАЛИДАМИ В ШКОЛАХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещены цели социальной защиты учащихся-инвалидов в школах, использование приемов и технологий социальной работы с ними, а также повышение чувства собственного достоинства, защита их прав и интересов, создание условий беспрепятственного обучения в человеческой среде, на основе социологических исследований о различных взаимоотношениях между микро-, мезо-, эко-, макроэлементами системы, которые прямо или косвенно оказывают социальное воздействие, обеспечение эффективной интеграции и инклюзивности общества. Также описан опыт зарубежных стран, теоретические его аспекты, активное участие социальных работников в школьном образовании путем совместной работы с учащимися, их семьями, учителями, общественностью и другими заинтересованными сторонами в создании здоровой и дружелюбной среды и тем самым обеспечении инклюзивного образования.

Ключевые слова: риск, инвалидность, специальное образование, исключение, сегрегация, интеграция, инклюзия, мультидисциплинарный подход поддержки, оценка, партнерство «школа-семья-соседство-сообщество», экологическая система, посредничество, группа сверстников, консенсус.

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, increasing human dignity, especially the issues of the disables are under constant attention, and consistent measures are taken to protect their rights and interests, create a barrier-free human environment, and effectively integrate them into society. Necessary legal and organizational conditions are being created for the active participation of people with disabilities in the political, social, economic and cultural life of the country. Especially, in recent years, the adoption of important decisions and decrees on this issue by the head of our state is of great

importance in protecting the rights and interests of disable people, relieving them of hopelessness and insecurity, and increasing their aspirations for life.

Integration of disable children into general education schools is a natural stage in the development of the inclusive education system. This is related to the recognition of the equal rights of children with disabilities by the society and the state, and the obligation of the society to provide such children with wide opportunities in various fields, including education. In particular, according to the provisions of Article 5 of the newly revised Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", everyone has equal rights to education [1]. This law differs from the previous one and includes the concept of inclusive (harmonized) education. Because, in our country, great attention is being paid to the fundamental reform of inclusive education as well as all other fields.

Inclusive education is derived from the English word: *inclusion* - to adapt, cooperative education [2], and means to eliminate barriers between children who need special attention and ordinary children. Inclusive education is an educational system that represents the involvement of adolescents in the educational process, aimed at adapting them to social life, regardless of developmental defects or economic difficulties. Inclusive education also offers a continuum of services to meet the diverse needs of disable students, including the most accessible learning environment. This principle means:

- all children should be integrated into the school education and social life where they live;
- it is necessary to create an educational environment that meets the needs of each child;
- to create a comprehensive support system in inclusive schools that allows not only children with disabilities, but also all children to achieve success, feel safe, and value being together in a team; The goal of such a school, imbued with humanism in the literal sense, is to create an environment of full social development for all students;
- to give students the opportunity to actively participate in the team and ensure mutual cooperation, help each other as members of society [3].

Summarizing the foreign experience of educating children with disabilities, in some countries there is a certain consensus on the importance of integrating children of this category into the community [4]. "Inclusive education" is an important direction in the activities of not only specialists in the field of education, but also leaders of the field, politicians, economists, human rights defenders, social workers (those who protect social justice and create equal opportunities for development of vulnerable members of society).

METHODOLOGY

In the special education literature, the term "Special Educational Needs" refers to the ability of a person to participate in and benefit from education in any setting due to physical, emotional, mental health, or other disabilities and indicates the possibility of not limiting the possibility. Also, it is necessary to pay special attention to the application in relation to categories, such as, children with special educational needs, students with disabilities, chronic diseases and children from stressed families, pregnant students and young mothers and it is important in the assessment of inclusiveness of education regarding the support [5].

In today's era of changes, it is of great importance to include all children in education and to create an educational environment that takes into account their needs. It is very important to identify the categories in need of inclusive education, to be able to correctly evaluate them and bring them into the general educational environment, as well as to provide social, medical and psychological services. In this process, some students with disabilities and in need of help (stressed children, teenage pregnant girls) are supported by offering individual education services.

In developed countries, students with disabilities have the right to study together with healthy peers in general schools in inclusive education. In particular, the following inclusive education services are provided to meet the needs of representatives of 13 categories of disabilities: autism, deaf-blindness, deafness, delayed development, emotional stress and depression, hearing loss, mental retardation, orthopedic diseases, health other health problems, speech disorders, brain damage, blindness, deafness.

It should be noted here that according to the results of the conducted sociological research, the needs of students with disabilities are more stable than normal students and they feel the need to form mutually adequate relationships. For this reason, schools must individualize their education to meet the unique needs of each student, as students with the same disability have different needs [6].

We use the approach of the social priority importance of education for children with disabilities in general educational institutions, not in special boarding schools or at home and this was put forward by G. Nam, a researcher on inclusive education [7].

In our opinion, social-medical-psychological services in the school to meet the special needs of students with disabilities should be directed not only to children with special needs, but to every student. Appropriate services include social, occupational and physical therapy, psychological counseling and medical diagnostic services necessary for the education of students with disabilities. This means that the social context of education and disability means that the professional activity of social work in the school is necessary. The school social worker acts as a liaison between the family-school-community in providing social services, directly or indirectly, to increase the academic and social success of students. Because social work at school promotes and supports inclusion, meets the individual needs of students with disabilities. In a word, social work at school is manifested in the creation of an equal educational environment for everyone. International experience also confirms this. In particular, L. Openshaw states that the main goal of school social workers is to help students and provide them with a suitable environment for optimizing the learning process [8]. It should be noted here that the roles and responsibilities of school social workers vary, with some working in the area of assessing the right to special education for persons with disabilities, others in developing treatment and intervention plans, and is engaged in implementation. Also, to ensure inclusive education, the school social worker can work in a variety of areas, such as school, city and district level management and change procedures, using different social work practices such as individual work, group work and school-community partnerships. bring to life.

According to English scientists K. Pryor, K. Kent, B. Roy and K. Gan, the main task of a social worker is mediation, that is, directing the execution of activities rather than having an indirect influence on the activity. They believe that their mediating functions are manifested in teamwork, solving student problems, and cooperating with teachers and parents [9]. We believe that limiting the functions of a social worker to mediation is completely incompatible with the goals of the activity. In our opinion, based on the above considerations, it is recommended that the following directions should be considered as the most important tasks of a social worker in inclusive education:

- protecting the rights of students with disabilities, fighting injustice and social restrictions that hinder their development;
- to ensure equal opportunities for children with special needs to become full-fledged members of society and contribute to them at the level of their abilities;
- to ensure that students with disabilities have full access to educational conditions, appropriate medical and social services, as well as vocational and employment opportunities;
- establishing contact with the families of students with disabilities, participating in determining the special needs of such students;
- providing information about the rights and possibilities of social and legal protection of students with special educational needs;
- identifying signs of violence against students and reporting to student protection authorities;
- consultation with the school management to adapt the school environment for students with disabilities;
- organization of educational trainings for students with disabilities, their parents and teachers;
- contacting various institutions for social and educational services, providing school mediation in conflict relations.

In the "ecological systems theory" developed by the American social work expert U. Bronfenbrenner, the child's development is notable for the priority of various motivational influences [10]. However, in this theory, not only motivation, but also the social environment, the genosociogram of the person, the roles of the social worker, the priority position of the teacher and

the family are insufficiently justified. Therefore, we bring to the attention of the scientific community an improved and revised activity scheme that systematically ensures student development (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. "School-family-neighborhood-community (mahalla)" cooperation and opportunities

Social factors that directly affect the development of the student's personality were analyzed on the basis of various relationships between the elements of the system. The impact of social factors includes the child with a disability, his characteristics, level of self-esteem, academic problems, and social status as an object of reflection.

The second element of the social influence on a child with disabilities is the microsystem element, which represents personal relationships, the child's family, school, neighborhood, peers.

The third important element is the mesosystem, which embodies the process by which school-family cooperation is formed and such loving relationships are supported. According to the rules of the US social work system, the lack of such contacts becomes a risk factor for the normal development of the student [11]. After all, the stronger the mutually supportive relations are between the systems, the greater the opportunities for healthy development will be.

The next element is the ecosystem, which includes the influence of broader social groups and institutions (such as school boards or community centers). Although the effects of this system do not directly affect the psyche, intellect, and well-being of a student, social and family events can have an indirect effect.

The final social element is a macrosystem that includes folk rituals, traditions, ideologies and cultural characteristics. Impacts in this system include the impact of socio-economic changes such as major historical events (e.g. wars) or the globalization of the economy. For example, the global economic crisis affects the state's economy, causing job losses and budget cuts for school programs.

Thus, ecological systems theory provides an important perspective on the role of the social worker in inclusive education, which includes a whole-of-community integrated approach in which the social worker addresses the needs of students with disabilities by connecting them to key resources. works as a supporting entity to satisfy.

From the point of view of the ecological system, the role of the social worker in the conditions of inclusive education is manifested in the formation of different knowledge of the student with disabilities. This perspective allows us to understand the different roles of the social worker in inclusive education. At the micro level, the school social worker can encourage interactions between

different systems such as school and family. From the meso to the macro level, social work works with groups, communities and relies on a social action approach to effect change at the policy level.

The knowledge needed for professional social workers in developed countries to work with students with disabilities and to build partnerships between their families and schools, as well as to engage the public in inclusive education practices, and skills to provide evidence-based interventions in the world of students and families by accurately assessing their needs and connecting them with adequate resources to help communities understand the purpose of inclusive education [12].

RESULTS

A number of additional functions for school social workers to facilitate inclusive education are also important. Additional services provided by school social workers are:

- school social workers advise students with disabilities and meet their needs at the individual, group and school level;

- school social workers help families get the necessary services or connect them with public institutions;

- another, most basic type of activity of a school social worker in support of inclusive education is to determine in detail their professional aspirations by assessing the special needs of students. Special attention is paid to the practice of diagnosis through the social work worker's assessment of the needs of students with disabilities.

Needs assessment is a broader process that lays the groundwork for developing school-based programs to meet the needs of students with disabilities. One of the most important roles of a social worker in providing inclusive education is to assess the needs of a student with a disability in order to plan for early intervention. Assessment is a comprehensive process that creates an environment that meets the diverse needs of students and develops intervention plans. Assessment of the needs of the student by the social worker requires the study of various aspects affecting the child and his environment, which must be carried out in order to benefit from the involvement of the student with disabilities in general education.

From the point of view of ecological theory, the role of the social worker is to understand the child in his general environment, taking into account not only the student's school environment, but also family, peers, friends and neighbors, in order to ensure inclusive education. In addition to providing inclusive education, it assesses the student with disabilities in terms of their strengths, discovers their strengths and uses them to achieve their academic goals [13].

A needs assessment is done holistically, taking into account the different systems that directly or indirectly affect the learner. Therefore, in assessing the various needs of the student, it is necessary to obtain information from the teachers about the student's problem, to learn from the parents sociological facts about the student's behavior in the family, the socio-economic conditions of the family, the structure of the family, and the financial situation. Sociological facts are used to collect information about the student's activities and behavior of relatives, friends and neighborhood. In the systematization of the student's problem, the social worker matches the needs of the student in various directions, for example, by providing direct services, counseling, and providing general inclusive education. It is necessary to strive to connect. They should also identify signs of violence in students and report to child protection authorities. Children with disabilities are deeply affected by traumatic events. Therefore, within the framework of this incident, the school social worker should conduct training and informative preventive measures with teachers, parents and peers to prevent alarming incidents.

Visiting the family is one of the main activities of a social worker. The practice of family visitation provides a wealth of useful information that can be used as a basis for an accurate assessment of a student's needs and risks. Also, family visits expand opportunities to understand the environment in the home and its impact on the student's educational activities. In Uzbekistan, family visits are carried out on the basis of public opinion formed in the neighborhood. However, in the USA and Europe, local residents do not form public opinion about people. For this reason, family visits are used from an ecological point of view to improve the situation in the individual household [14].

Family visits are very useful when working with children with disabilities. When social workers visit the student's family, they understand the environment of the student outside the educational institution, understand their roles and responsibilities in relation to the special needs of children, which leads to quality inclusive education. Because students with disabilities in schools, despite having all the necessary support, face obstacles, which is related to various factors in their family situation. Therefore, the reasons behind these problems can be known and understood by visiting the family. It should be emphasized that pedagogues have a significant contribution in maintaining the relationship between school and family. In the Western world, we see the opposite. According to M. Davitt, a major specialist in the field of social work in Australian schools, teachers deal with the educational needs of students, so another specialist should work in direct contact with parents. It shows that giving this role to teachers will put excessive pressure on them and have a harmful effect on their teaching. Also, in Australia and a number of countries, social workers are mainly engaged in providing social and educational counseling to help children with special needs. For this, a social worker regularly conducts special consultations.

Various problems are identified by students, parents and teachers at such an event. A social worker's family-school partnership reveals a student's strengths as well as weaknesses and special needs, which helps to plan and strategize an inclusive educational environment that meets the student's needs and potential. In order to achieve the effectiveness of inclusive education, mediation is used in interpersonal relations with the aim of mutual restraint, resistance, in a word, reaching a compromise. According to the Portuguese sociologist Piero Bertolini, mediation provides the initial connection between education and he understands mediation as establishing interpersonal relationships [15].

In Uzbekistan, the role of social worker mediation (mediation) in inclusive education has the goal of stabilizing, intensively establishing relations between parents and schools, achieving harmony, in a word, reaching consensus. Mediation involves the development of connections between various systems that affect the student, the integration of the student and his social world into this system, and the activation of the activities of parents, classmates, peers, friends and students.

Mediation requires special knowledge and skills and must ensure the right relationship between family-school-community to make positive changes in the field of inclusive education. After all, the common goal of mediation and social work is to further expand the opportunities of students with disabilities based on the principle of objectivity, justice and social welfare. A social worker who uses mediation creates a shared consensus and understanding between the systems that affect a student with a disability and his or her education. Within the framework of ecological theory, mediation can be used as a tool to solve students' problems related to the systems in which they live. One of the methods of mediation (mediation) used by social workers to ensure inclusive education is peer mediation. It represents teaching students with disabilities to be adaptive and interactive with their peers. In this process, social workers use role plays, modeling, and specific instructions to create awareness among peer groups. It helps to create a peer group that acts as a social mediator in educational institutions. Social workers in the role of mediation adhere to the principles of neutrality, confidentiality and impartiality. Social workers act as mediators in conflict resolution to advise, guide, advocate and support the parties involved in offering inclusive education to a child with special needs [16].

It is possible to enrich the resource base by providing important information to the participants of the social worker training process and developing mutual relations between them. In this sense, it is important to analyze the children with special educational needs into the main diagnostic groups in order to determine in detail the professional intervention of school social workers.

A multidisciplinary team approach is of great importance in providing inclusive education. The contribution of a social worker in multidisciplinary teams is great and is mainly manifested in the coordination of activities. His role in ecological systems theory works with the various systems that affect the individual in need, developing an appropriate intervention model to increase the intensity of the inclusive education field. Also, the social worker helps to correctly distribute the tasks

of working in a multidisciplinary team, information about the activities of different teams is collected in order to make effective decisions for students with special needs [17].

According to the National Association of Social Work (NASW) standards, it is critical that school social workers provide interprofessional leadership and collaboration by working with other school personnel, parents, and the community to improve the lives and academic outcomes of students.

Care and support services in schools are based on a coordinated multidisciplinary approach in the policy of education through inclusion in the education system in Uzbekistan. Researcher S. Allen is a multidisciplinary team of social workers and various professionals emphasizes that the motivation to perform common tasks together is very necessary to assess the student's ability [18].

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Sociologist R. Kemp shows that the inclusion approach is important, working together in a multidisciplinary group is a solution to providing medical, therapeutic, psychological and social assistance to the student [20]. Also, B. D. Bois and K. Miles emphasize that qualified counselors and experienced persons play a decisive role in effectively directing the activities of school social workers, it is explained that such an approach is beneficial in both traditional and modern societies [21].

The English sociologist R. Kemp states that qualified counselors do not show themselves in any situation in multidisciplinary teams, and are responsible for intervention only when there are problematic situations and actions that negatively affect the child's academic performance [22]. He claims that he is an expert, A multidisciplinary support group is a social management structure at the regional level (Fig. 2).

2 – figure. Multidisciplinary support team

Their role is to direct and coordinate services in the child's best interest. In addition, these services include advice on how to adapt to the school environment, meetings with families for the best interests of the child, and guidance on how to deal with specific problems of children. Area support teams must keep parents informed of the student's support status, provide updates and evidence, and deliver the most appropriate support to meet needs without delay [23].

Another important role of a social worker in working with children with disabilities at school is the role of advocate. The role of advocacy is one of the defining elements of social work as a profession. Inclusive education required the social worker to protect the rights of the learner to ensure equal access to educational resources and opportunities for every child. The role of the social worker is not only to liaise between different systems to meet the needs of students, children, but also to ensure justice and promote equality by protecting their rights, reducing stigma and enabling them to take their place in society [24].

Thus, social workers act as a supportive sub-sector to implement changes that effectively respond to the needs of students, families, and the school system. They advocate for the full realization and provision of the right of every student and child to education, their general physiological, intellectual and spiritual growth and development, dignity, abilities and potential. plays the role of a worshiper. A social worker must advocate for the provision of services that must be available to meet the child's socio-educational needs in an inclusive setting.

CONCLUSION

A brief description of the main professional activities of school social workers in supporting inclusive education is as follows:

- participation in determining special needs in the school area;
- help in communication with families of children with special educational needs in the school area;
- social and legal protection of students with special educational needs, providing relevant information to families about their rights and opportunities;
- directing parents and students with disabilities to enter general secondary schools, providing them with detailed information on this matter;
- to identify traces of violence against students with disabilities, to report this to the child protection authorities;
- conducting individual and group meetings on various issues with all students, including children with disabilities;
- proactively organize and provide favorable conditions for the school environment to welcome the child mentally and educationally;
- organization of information companies and trainings for students, parents and teachers;
- to establish permanent contact with various institutions for the organization of social and educational services in society;
- providing school mediation (mediation) in conflict relations;
- help in organizing access to specialized transport for students with disabilities.

The above activity, work, tasks and obligations express the social necessity of establishing the activity of a school social worker, which expresses the urgent need for this specialist in the school.

Therefore, inclusive education requires social workers to have the skills to work with individuals, groups, families and communities. It is known that limited medical resources for students with disabilities lead to their slow development compared to other children. The main professional activity of a social worker is to establish close cooperation with teachers and help students to develop high-level social skills, behavior and interpersonal awareness. Also, to encourage students with disabilities to communicate sincerely with their peers, to help strengthen mutual relations between them, to improve the social and moral skills of students and parents. The activity of conducting training sessions is also important.

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6 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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